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CONTENT OF THE PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING OF CHESS PLAYERS

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Annotation: The article deals with the issues of psychological preparation of chess players of all levels. Today, the training of chess players of all levels is one of the most urgent problems. Since chess is a sport that is gaining more and more popularity.

Key words: chess, psychological preparation, moral and volitional qualities, sports training system.

Introduction. Currently, chess is gaining more and more popularity in the world. Now many countries include chess in the education program. Many begin to learn this complex and multifaceted game from early childhood, and many children dream of becoming world chess champions, but not everyone succeeds. In recent years, opportunities and tools have appeared that allow young chess players to significantly shorten the path to the heights of chess mastery [1, 2].

With the advent of computers, the processes of collecting, storing, and transmitting information can be carried out much more efficiently. If earlier the coach collected books, magazines, diagrams, then with the advent of computer chess programs, the functions of assembling and storing information became much easier and more convenient [3, 4]. Moreover, programs can act as an assistant to a coach, that is, to train young chess players. Therefore, many of the best chess players in the world do not do their preparation for competitions without the help of a computer and computer chess programs [5, 6]. The presence of the Internet has made information accessible to all chess players, whereas earlier access to information in many countries was difficult, now it is a matter of pressing a button on the keyboard. Those chess players who continue to train according to the traditional method will lag far behind the chess players who combine the traditional method of preparation with the help of a computer. The use of computer programs can significantly reduce the time for mastering tactical skills and the technique of calculating options, as well as increase the motor density of learning [7, 8].

Today, the training of high-class chess players is one of the most urgent problems. Since chess is a sport that is gaining more and more popularity, and, consequently, because of this, its status in the sports environment is increasing [9, 10, 11]. The most important aspects of the training of athletes are given much attention by specialists in the field of physical culture and sports. These include the works of L. P. Matveev, N. V. Krogus, S. A. Lysenko, Yu. I. Smirnov, I. V. Mikhailova, A. N.

Neverkovich. For example, training is characterized as an important process of using a variety of factors (means, methods, conditions) that will help an athlete to prepare well and be aimed at a high result [12, 13, 14].

The system of sports training can be divided into:

- 1) Competition system.
- 2) Training system.
- 3) Factors that increase the effectiveness of training and competitive activities [15].

Psychological training can be attributed to the first and second points, that is, to the training system, which, in addition to it, includes physical training, sports and technical, tactical, education, and intellectual development [16, 17].

One of the main stages of preparation is planning, which should reflect the plan according to which the preparation will be built. The most important form will be sports training, which will include training with a coach and self-study. In general, sports training can be described as a purposeful process that is aimed at improving certain abilities and helping to achieve high sports results in the future. The preparation factors include participation in competitions, which are an integral part of sports training. The main goal of sports training is preparation for competitions, with the help of which the athlete will be able to show the highest result [18, 19].

Many experts argue that competition is primarily a struggle of feelings, emotions, physical perfection, which for the most part takes place on a mental level. And as often happens, the winner is the one who, as they say, turned out to have stronger nerves, although the athlete may have been lower in class than others. After all, competition is an activity that takes place in extreme conditions [20].

Thus, V. B. Kramnik, the fourteenth world champion, claims that “chess in terms of its loads, and in particular mental, is on a par with hard physical labor. And the psychological state in which you enter the tournament will be the result of the preparation that was carried out earlier.” Therefore, one cannot but agree with the opinion that the result of an activity depends on the emotional and psychological attitude to this activity.

Chess is a very valuable subject for research in the field of psychology. But oddly enough, there are very few scientific and methodological manuals for preparing chess players for competitions. Preparation for competitions includes the study of both individual mental functions and the study of a person as a whole. The training of chess players is a psychological and pedagogical process that takes place under the influence of mental stress, and helps to develop many mental

qualities. The main goal of psychological preparation in training chess players is a system that will help an athlete achieve the highest result [21, 22].

Based on this, it is possible to define psychological preparation as the development and education of a personality, the development of qualities that contribute to the use of physical and psychological stress to achieve results. The task of psychological preparation is a harmonious combination of physical and psychological preparation, as well as the use of purely chess aspects for the upcoming struggle in the tournament. After all, each athlete has a different level of preparedness, and it is how an individual player will combine all kinds of acquired knowledge in terms of psychology, and will determine his tournament success.

Conclusions. For a systematic consideration of the problem of psychological preparation of chess players, it is necessary to pay attention to the pre-start state, the correct process of preparation, and understanding of the opponent. Many today believe that psychology plays no role in chess or, if it does, then only a small one, but how then can blunders and overlooks and so on be explained, these are just the simplest examples.

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